

Fractional spin through quantum strange superalgebra $\tilde{P}_Q(n)$.

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Abstract

The purposes of this paper is to investigate the properties of the quantum extended strange superalgebra $\tilde{P}_Q(n)$ when his deformation parameter Q goes to a root of unity.

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1 Introduction

In recent years, much interest has been made in the study of the Lie superalgebras [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6]. These structures can be obtained through consistent realization involving deformed Bose and Fermi operators [7, 8].

In another vein, the geometric interpretation of fractional supersymmetry have gaining increased attention, particularly in the works [9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15], where the authors show that the one-dimensional superspace is equivalent to the braided line when the deformation parameter goes to a root of unity $Q \rightarrow q$, and the braided line is generated by a generalized odd variable and a (classical)ordinary even variable. In the work [16], R. S. Dunne, using Q -oscillator realization, proved that the $U_Q(sl(2))$ is similar to a direct product of the finite classical algebra $U(sl(2))$ and the q -deformed one $U_q(sl(2))$ (where q is a root of unity).

Since there exist Q -oscillator realization of all deformed algebras and deformed super algebras $U_Q(g)$, it is convenient to explore the splitting of these (super) algebras when $Q \rightarrow q$. In this context, the property of splitting of some particular quantum (Super)-algebras was examined in [18]. The decomposition of the quantum (super) Virasoro algebras is described in [19]. The case of quantum affine algebras with vanishing central charge is developed in [20] and the case quantum algebras A_n, B_n, C_n and D_n and quantum superalgebra $A(m, n), B(m, n), C(n + 1)$ and $D(n, m)$ in the $Q \rightarrow q$ limit is investigated in [21].

The Lie superalgebras of classical type are one of the two following classes[22]: basic Lie superalgebras or strange ones. The basic Lie superalgebras have properties like as simple Lie algebras. They have an invariant non-degenerate bilinear form, but strange Lie superalgebras $P(n)$ and $Q(n)$ haven't.

The strange Lie superalgebra $P(n)$ have attracted a particularly attention. In [23], Dynkin-like diagrams of the strange superalgebra $P(n)$ was examined by Frappat, Sciarrino and Sorba. In [24], polynomial representations of strange Lie superalgebras are investigated. The oscillator realization of the strange superalgebras $P(n)$ has been constructed by Frappat, Sciarrino and Sorba in [25]. A deformation $U_Q(\tilde{P}(n)) = \tilde{P}_Q(n)$ of the extended non-contragredient (strange) superalgebra $\tilde{P}(n)$ is given in [26].

The purpose of this paper is to explore the property of decomposition of the quantum extended non-contragredient (strange) superalgebra $U_Q(\tilde{P}(n)) = \tilde{P}_Q(n)$ in the $Q \rightarrow q$ limit. In next section (section 2) we review some results concerning k -fermions, decomposition property of Q -boson in the $Q \rightarrow q$ limit and the equivalence between Q -deformed fermions and classical ones. Using these results detailed in [19, 20], we analyse the $Q \rightarrow q$ limit of the quantum $U_Q(sl(n))$ algebra of the $sl(n)$ algebra (The bosonic part of $P(n)$) (section 3) and the quantum extended non-contragredient (strange) superalgebra of $U_Q(\tilde{P}(n))$ (section 4). In the last section (section 5) we shall give some concluding remarks

2 Preliminaries

In this section we recall some basic facts about k -fermions[17], decomposition property of Q -boson in the $Q \rightarrow q$ limit and the equivalence between Q -deformed fermions and ordinary ones (see [19, 20] for more details).

Let us began by giving the definition of the Q -bosonic algebra noted (Ξ_Q^i) , generated by a number operator N_{A_i} , a creation operator A_i^+ and an annihilation operator A_i^- , satisfying the relations:

$$\begin{aligned} A_i^- A_i^+ - Q^\pm A_i^+ A_i^- &= Q^{\mp N_{A_i}} \\ Q^{N_{A_i}} A_i^\pm Q^{-N_{A_i}} &= Q^\pm A_i^\pm \\ Q^{N_{A_i}} Q^{-N_{A_i}} &= Q^{-N_{A_i}} Q^{+N_{A_i}} = 1 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

then if we put the following operators as given in [16]:

$$a_i^- = \lim_{Q \rightarrow q} \frac{Q^{\pm \frac{kN_{A_i}}{2}}}{([k!]^{\frac{1}{2}})} (A_i^-)^k, \quad a_i^+ = \lim_{Q \rightarrow q} \frac{(A_i^+)^k Q^{\pm \frac{kN_{A_i}}{2}}}{([k!]^{\frac{1}{2}})}, \quad (2)$$

we can easily show that the above operators (2) gratifies the relations of an ordinary boson algebra noted Ξ_0^i , defined by:

$$\begin{aligned} [a_i^-, a_i^+] &= 1. \\ [N_{a_i}, a_i^\pm] &= \pm a_i^\pm \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The number operator of this new algebra is defined by $N_{a_i} = a_i^+ a_i^-$.

In order to discuss the splitting of Q -deformed boson in the limit $Q \rightarrow q$, we introduce the new operators:

$$\begin{aligned} \chi_i^- &= A_i^- q^{-\frac{kN_{A_i}}{2}} \\ \chi_i^+ &= A_i^+ q^{-\frac{kN_{A_i}}{2}} \\ N_{\chi_i} &= N_{A_i} - kN_{a_i}, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

which satisfies the relations of a k -fermionic algebra noted (Σ_q^i) defined by

$$\begin{aligned} [\chi_i^+, \chi_i^-]_{q^{-1}} &= q^{N_{\chi_i}} \\ [\chi_i^-, \chi_i^+]_q &= q^{-N_{\chi_i}} \\ [N_{\chi_i}, \chi_i^\pm] &= \pm \chi_i^\pm. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where the deformation parameter $q = e^{\frac{2i\pi}{r}}$, $r \in N - \{0, 1\}$, is a root of unity.

It straightforward to check that the two algebras generated respectively by the set of operators $\{a_i^+, a_i^-, N_{a_i}\}$ and $\{\chi_i^+, \chi_i^-, N_{\chi_i}\}$ are mutually commutative. We conclude that in the limit $Q \rightarrow q$, the Q -deformed bosonic algebra oscillator Ξ_Q^i decomposes into two independent algebras, an ordinary boson algebra Ξ_0^i and k -fermionic algebra Σ_q^i ; formally one can write:

$$\lim_{Q \rightarrow q} \Xi_Q^i \equiv \Xi_0^i \otimes \Sigma_q^i,$$

We define also the Q -deformed fermionic algebra noted Ω_Q generated by the generators Φ_i^-, Φ_i^+ and $Q^{M_{\Phi_i}}, Q^{-M_{\Phi_i}}$ satisfying the following relations

$$\begin{aligned}
Q^{M_{\Phi_i}} Q^{-M_{\Phi_i}} &= Q^{-M_{\Phi_i}} Q^{M_{\Phi_i}} = 1 \\
Q^{M_{\Phi_i}} Q^{M_{\Phi_j}} &= Q^{M_{\Phi_j}} Q^{M_{\Phi_i}} \\
Q^{M_{\Phi_i}} \Phi_i^\pm Q^{-M_{\Phi_i}} &= Q^{\pm \delta_{ij}} \Phi_j^\pm \\
\Phi_i^- \Phi_i^+ + Q^\pm \Phi_i^+ \Phi_i^- &= Q^{\pm M_i} \\
\{\Phi_i^\pm, \Phi_i^\pm\} &= 0; \\
(\Phi^+)^2 &= 0, (\Phi^-)^2 = 0 \\
\{\Phi_i^+, \Phi_j^-\} &= 0 \quad \text{for } i \neq j
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

then if put the new generators

$$\begin{aligned}
\phi_i^- &= Q^{\frac{-M_{\phi_i}}{2}} \Phi_i^- \\
\phi_i^+ &= \Phi_i^+ Q^{\frac{-M_{\phi_i}}{2}}
\end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

we see that the Q -deformed fermion reproduces an ordinary fermion algebra defined by the new operators (7) and the following relations

$$\begin{aligned}
(\phi_i^-)^2 &= 0 \\
(\phi_j^+)^2 &= 0 \\
\{\phi_i^-, \phi_j^+\} &= \delta_{ij}
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

3 The quantum algebra $U_Q(sl(n))$

Let $C = [a_{ij}] (1 \leq i, j \leq n)$ be a symmetrisable generalized Cartan matrix and let $d_i (1 \leq i \leq n)$ be the non integers such that $d_i a_{ij} = a_{ij} d_i$. Let $Q \neq 0$ be a complex number. For Q generic the quantum enveloping algebra corresponding to $[a_{ij}]$ is a Hopf algebra with 1 and generators $\{E_i, F_i, K_i^+ = Q^{+d_i H_i}, K_i^- = Q^{-d_i H_i}; 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ satisfying the following relations :

$$\begin{aligned}
[E_i, F_j] &= \delta_{ij} \frac{K_i - K_i^{-1}}{Q^{d_i} - Q^{-d_i}} \\
K_i E_j K_i^{-1} &= Q^{d_i a_{ij}} E_j \\
K_i F_j K_i^{-1} &= Q^{-d_i a_{ij}} F_j \\
K_i^- K_i^+ &= K_i^+ K_i^-; K_i K_j = K_j K_i
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

with Serre relations,

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{0 \leq t \leq n} (-1)^t \binom{n}{t}_Q (E_i)^t E_j (E_i)^{n-t} &= 0, & i \neq j \\
\sum_{0 \leq t \leq n} (-1)^t \binom{n}{t}_Q (F_i)^t F_j (F_i)^{n-t} &= 0, & i \neq j
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

where a_{ij} is Cartan matrix, $n = 1 - a_{ij}$ and

$$\binom{n}{t}_Q = \frac{[n]_Q!}{[t]_Q! [n-t]_Q!}, \quad [t]_Q! = [t]_Q [t-1]_Q \dots [1]_Q, \quad [t]_Q = \frac{Q^t - Q^{-t}}{Q - Q^{-1}} \tag{11}$$

The Cartan matrices of classical type A_n, B_n, C_n and D_n and the corresponding non zero integers are given in [27]. A discussion of the Q -boson and Q -fermion representation was given by Hayashi [28].

We focus here on the algebra $U_Q(sl(n))$ (where $sl(n)$ is the bosonic part of $P(n+1)$) and we

assume that the deformation parameter Q is generic. The explicit expressions for corresponding generators as linear and bilinear in Q -deformed bosonic operators are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} E_i &= A_i^- A_{i+1}^+ \\ F_i &= A_i^+ A_{i+1}^- \\ H_i &= -N_{A_i} + N_{A_{i+1}} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Now we can explore the *limit* $Q \rightarrow q$ of the quantum algebra $U_Q(sl(n))$. The key tool to discuss this *limit* is the Q -bosonic decomposition presented in detail in [19, 20] when the deformation parameter Q goes to a root of unity q . So, the n Q -bosons reproduce n ordinary bosons and n k -fermions $\{\chi_i^+; \chi_i^-; N_{\chi_i}\}$ with $(1 \leq i \leq n-1)$. The n classical bosons are defined by

$$a_i^- = \lim_{Q \rightarrow q} \frac{Q^{\pm \frac{kN_{A_i}}{2}}}{([k]!)^{\frac{1}{2}}} (A_i^-)^k, \quad a_i^+ = \lim_{Q \rightarrow q} \frac{(A_i^+)^k Q^{\pm \frac{kN_{A_i}}{2}}}{([k]!)^{\frac{1}{2}}}, \quad (13)$$

where their number operators are given by $N_{a_i} = a_i^+ a_i^-$, *for* $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

Then, using operators (13), we can construct the classical $U(sl(n))$ algebra (with $1 \leq i \leq n-1$):

$$\begin{aligned} e_i &= a_i^- a_{i+1}^+ \\ f_i &= a_i^+ a_{i+1}^- \\ h_i &= -N_{a_i} + N_{a_{i+1}} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

From the remaining operators $\{\chi_i^+; \chi_i^-; N_{\chi_i}\}$ with $(1 \leq i \leq n-1)$ we construct the new generators

$$\begin{aligned} E_i &= \chi_i^- \chi_{i+1}^+ \\ F_i &= \chi_i^+ \chi_{i+1}^- \\ H_i &= -N_{\chi_i} + N_{\chi_{i+1}} \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

which realize the $U_q(sl(n))$ algebra; where $U_q(sl(n))$ is the same version of $U_Q(sl(n))$ obtained by simply setting $Q = q$ rather than by taking the *limit* as above. The elements of $U_q(sl(n))$ and $U(sl(n))$ algebras are mutually commutative.

Then, in the $Q \rightarrow q$ *limit*, the quantum algebra $U_Q(sl(n))$ is a direct product of the form

$$\lim_{Q \rightarrow q} U_Q(sl(n)) = U_q(sl(n)) \otimes U(sl(n)) \quad (16)$$

Note that, the above direct product $\lim_{Q \rightarrow q} U_Q(g) = U_q(g) \otimes U(g)$ valid for quantum algebras does not appear of a quantum superalgebra $U_Q(\mathfrak{g})$. In fact the explicit expressions of the generators of the quantum superalgebra $U_Q(\mathfrak{g})$ are presented as linears and bilinears in Q -deformed bosonic and fermionic oscillator operators, and using the fact that the Q -deformed bosonic operators $\{A_i^+, A_i^-, N_{A_i}\}$ with $(1 \leq i \leq n)$ decomposes into two independent oscillators algebras: classical bosons $\{a_i^+, a_i^-, N_{a_i}\}$ and k -fermion operators $\{\chi_i^+, \chi_i^-, N_{\chi_i}\}$, and Q -fermions become q -fermions which are object equivalent to conventional fermions $\{\phi_i^+, \phi_i^-, M_{\phi_i}\}$. Then from the classical bosons $\{a_i^-, a_i^+, N_{a_i}\}$ and classical fermions $\{\phi_i^-, \phi_i^+, M_{\phi_i}\}$, one can realize the nondeformed superalgebra $U(\mathfrak{g})$ but from the remaining operators $\{\chi_i^-, \chi_i^-, N_{\chi_i}\}$ we construct the generators of a different quantum q -algebra (see [21] for more details).

4 The quantum extended strange superalgebra $\tilde{P}_Q(n)$

Let $G = G_0 \oplus G_1$ be a \mathbb{Z}_2 -graded vector space with $\dim G_0 = j$ and $\dim G_1 = i$. Then there exists a natural superalgebra structure on the algebra $End G$ defined by:

$$End G = End_0 G \oplus End_1 G \quad \text{where } End_k G = \{\phi \in End G \mid \phi(G_l) \subset G_{k+l}\}$$

The superalgebra $End G$ supplied with the Lie superbracket is the Lie superalgebra noted $\ell(i, j)$. The elements M of $\ell(i, j)$ have the form

$$M = \begin{pmatrix} N & Q \\ R & S \end{pmatrix}$$

where N and S are $gl(j)$ and $gl(i)$ matrices, Q and R are $j \times i$ and $i \times j$ rectangular matrices.

The superalgebra of matrices $M \in \ell(n, n)$ satisfying the following equalities

$$N^t = -S, \quad Q^t = Q, \quad R^t = -R, \quad \text{tr}(N) = 0$$

is nothing other than the (non contragredient) strange superalgebra $P(n)$.

An oscillator realization of the generators of $P(n)$ given in [2, 25]. In the Chevalley basis, the (non contragredient) strange superalgebra $P(n)$ is spanned by the generators $\{X_i, Y_i, T_i, X_n\}$ with $(1 \leq i \leq n-1)$ satisfying the following commutation relations:

$$\begin{aligned} [X_i, Y_j] &= \delta_{ij} T_i \\ [X_i, T_j] &= -a_{ij} X_i \\ [Y_i, T_j] &= a_{ij} Y_i \\ [T_i, X_n] &= a_{in} X_n \\ [T_i, T_j] &= 0 \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

where $(a_{ij})_{1 \leq i, j \leq n}$ is the Cartan matrix of $su(n)$ and $a_{in} = 0$ for $1 \leq i \leq n-2$ and $a_{n-1, n} = -2$.

Let us to precise that the notions of Dynkin diagram and Cartan matrix are not determined for the non-contragredient Lie superalgebra $P(n)$. However, if we extend the superalgebra of $P(n)$ by an appropriate diagonal matrices, one can obtain a non-null bilinear form on the Cartan subalgebra of this extension and therefore get in this case a generalized form of the notions of Cartan matrix and Dynkin diagram [2].

The extended strange superalgebra $\tilde{P}(n)$ is defined in this basis by $3(n-1)$ bosonic generators X_i, Y_i, T_i , with $i = 1, \dots, n-1$, and a fermionic generator X_n and a diagonal generator D such that

$$\begin{aligned} [X_i, Y_j] &= \delta_{ij} T_i \\ [X_i, T_j] &= -a_{ij} X_i \\ [Y_i, T_j] &= a_{ij} Y_i; \\ [T_i, X_n] &= a_{in} X_n; \\ [T_i, T_j] &= 0; \\ [D, X_i] &= [D, Y_i] = [D, T_i] = 0 \\ [D, X_n] &= X_n \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

The Cartan matrix of the extended strange superalgebra $(a_{ik})_{\tilde{P}(n)}$ of $\tilde{P}(n)$ with $1 \leq i \leq n-1$

and $1 \leq k \leq n$ is given by:

$$(a_{ik})_{\tilde{P}(n)} = \begin{pmatrix} 2 & -1 & 0 & \cdots & \cdots & & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 2 & -1 & & & & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & 0 & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & & & & & & & \\ & & & & & & 2 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & & \cdots & 0 & -1 & 2 & -2 \end{pmatrix}$$

The Cartan matrix is well defined to get the Serre relations for the extended non-contragredient Lie superalgebra $\tilde{P}(n)$ in the quantum case and permits to define a quantum superalgebra structure on the Q -deformed version of the extended non-contragredient (strange) superalgebra $\tilde{P}(n)$.

For Q generic, a quantum deformation $U_Q(\tilde{P}(n)) = \tilde{P}_Q(n)$ of the extended non-contragredient (strange) superalgebra $\tilde{P}(n)$ is proposed in [26] as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} [\hat{X}_i, \hat{Y}_j] &= \delta_{ij}[\hat{T}_i]_Q \\ [\hat{T}_i, \hat{X}_n] &= a_{in}\hat{X}_i \\ [\hat{Y}_i, \hat{T}_j] &= a_{ij}\hat{Y}_i \\ [\hat{T}_i, \hat{T}_j] &= 0 \\ [\hat{D}, \hat{X}_i] &= [\hat{D}, \hat{Y}_i] = [\hat{D}, \hat{T}_i] = 0 \\ [\hat{D}, \hat{X}_n] &= \hat{X}_n \\ [\hat{X}_i, \hat{T}_j] &= -a_{ij}\hat{X}_i \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

and the quantum Serre relations described by the expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{0 \leq t \leq 1-a_{ik}} (-1)^t \begin{bmatrix} 1-a_{ik} \\ t \end{bmatrix} \hat{X}_i^{1-a_{ik}-t} \hat{X}_k \hat{X}_i^t &= 0 \\ \sum_{0 \leq t \leq 1-a_{ij}} (-1)^t \begin{bmatrix} 1-a_{ij} \\ t \end{bmatrix} \hat{Y}_i^{1-a_{ij}-t} \hat{Y}_j \hat{Y}_i^t &= 0 \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

A possible realization of the generators of $\tilde{P}_Q(n)$ in terms of the Q -deformed oscillators $\{\Phi_i^-, \Phi_i^+, M_{\Phi_i}\}$ and $\{A_i^+, A_i^-, N_{A_i}\}$ with $(1 \leq i \leq n)$ is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{X}_i &= A_i^+ A_{i+1}^- Q^{\frac{(M_{\Phi_i} - M_{\Phi_{i+1}})}{2}} + \Phi_i^+ \Phi_{i+1}^- Q^{\frac{-(N_{A_i} - N_{A_{i+1}})}{2}} \\ \hat{X}_n &= A_n^+ \Phi_n^+ Q^{\left(\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} N_{A_i} - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} M_{\Phi_i}\right)} \\ \hat{Y}_i &= A_{i+1}^+ A_i^- Q^{\frac{(M_{A_i} - M_{A_{i+1}})}{2}} + \Phi_{i+1}^+ \Phi_i^- Q^{\frac{-(N_{\Phi_i} - N_{\Phi_{i+1}})}{2}} \\ \hat{T}_i &= N_{A_i} - N_{A_{i+1}} + M_{\Phi_i} - M_{\Phi_{i+1}} \\ \hat{D} &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n N_{A_i} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n M_{\Phi_i} \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

where A_i^+ and A_i^- are the Q -deformed bosonic algebra operators and Φ_i^+ and Φ_i^- are the Q -deformed fermionic ones.

Using the fact that in $Q \rightarrow q$ limit, the Q -deformed boson algebras $\{A_i^+, A_i^-, N_{A_i}\}$ reproduces classical bosons algebras $\{a_i^+, a_i^-, N_{a_i}\}$ and a q -deformed k -fermions generators $\{\chi_i^+, \chi_i^-, N_{\chi_i}\}$, and in this limit the Q -fermions become q -fermions which are object equivalent to classical ones $\{\phi_i^+, \phi_i^-, M_{\phi_i}\}$, then from the classical bosons $\{a_i^-, a_i^+, N_{a_i}\}$ and classical fermions $\{\phi_i^-, \phi_i^+, M_{\phi_i}\}$, one can construct the classical extended strange superalgebra $\tilde{P}(n)$:

$$\begin{aligned} X_i &= a_i^+ a_{i+1}^- + \phi_i^+ \phi_{i+1}^- \\ X_n &= a_n^+ \phi_n^+ \\ Y_i &= a_{i+1}^+ a_i^- + \phi_{i+1}^+ \phi_i^- \\ T_i &= N_{a_i} - N_{a_{i+1}} + M_{\phi_i} - M_{\phi_{i+1}} \\ D &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n N_{a_i} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n M_{\phi_i} \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

From the remaining operators $\{\chi_i^-, \chi_i^-, N_{\chi_i}\}$ we realize the following :

$$\begin{aligned} E_i &= \chi_i^- \chi_{i+1}^+, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n-1 \\ F_i &= \chi_i^+ \chi_{i+1}^-, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n-1 \\ K_i &= q^{-N_{\chi_i} + N_{\chi_{i+1}}}, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n-1 \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

which generates the q -deformed algebra $U_q(sl(n))$. It is easy to show that $U_q(sl(n))$ and $\tilde{P}(n)$ are mutually commutative. As results, we obtain the following decomposition of the quantum strange superalgebra $\tilde{P}_Q(n)$ in the $Q \rightarrow q$ limit

$$\lim_{Q \rightarrow q} \tilde{P}_Q(n) = U_q(sl(n)) \otimes \tilde{P}(n). \quad (24)$$

5 Conclusion

It is important to note that we have established this decomposition of the quantum strange superalgebra $\tilde{P}_Q(n)$ only for a particular realization, i.e, the Q -oscillator realization and although the quantum extended strange superalgebra $\tilde{P}_Q(n)$ does not have direct product form, we establish, for this realization and the corresponding highest weight representations the decomposition of $\tilde{P}_Q(n)$ into the direct product of undeformed $\tilde{P}(n)$ and $U_q(sl(n))$ (the naive version of $U_q(sl(n))$ at $Q = q$ obtained by simply setting $Q = q$). The labels of the highest weight representations of the quantum strange superalgebra $\tilde{P}_Q(n)$ and the choice of the basis in which the decomposition (24) is clearly manifested will be investigated elsewhere.

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